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Influence of Blended Learning Models on Postgraduate Students' Academic Performance of Educational Management, Rivers State Universities, Port Harcourt

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ABSTRACT

The study centred on influence of Blended Learning Models on Postgraduate Students' Academic Performance of Educational Management, Rivers State Universities, Port Harcourt. Thus, four research questions and four hypotheses were drawn for the study. The study adopted descriptive design. The population of the study was two hundred and twenty-five (225) lecturers and postgraduate students in the Department of Educational Management, Rivers State Universities. The sample of the study is 225 (lecturers and students) respondents. The instrument was titled: Blended Learning Model and Post Graduate Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (BLMPGSAPQ). Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to achieve reliability index of 0.74, 0.82, 0.77 and 0.87. Thus, 225 copies of questionnaire were administered and retrieved (195) for the analysis of research questions and hypotheses. The data gathered from the instrument, Blended Learning Model and Post Graduate Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (BLMPGSAPQ) was analyzed using mean score. The hypotheses were tested using z -test. The findings indicated that blended learning model of learning influences academic performance of students of educational management to a high extent. The hypotheses revealed that no significant difference exist in opinion of respondents on how blended learning model influence Academic Performance of Post Graduate Students. Based on the findings, it was concluded that Blended learning method increased flexibility and independence of learning activities. It was therefore recommended that rotational model of teaching should be adopted to enhance the potentialities of post graduate students of educational management. In addition, there should be application of team teaching to authenticate flexible learning activities within and outside the school environment.

Keywords: Blended Learning, academic performance, Post Graduate Students

INTRODUCTION

Education is one of the sectors that have undergone several changes over a period of time. It is no longer just lecturers engaging students or students sitting silently and taking notes. It is more active now than before in terms of conducting teaching and learning. For instance, for effective teaching and learning, there is integration or blending of academic activities that will captivate the interest of students for expected performance through virtual class activities, Google Classroom, Zoom, Google Meet, Webex, and other media of instructional activities. This implies that the process of conducting learning is no

longer teacher-centered but student-centered, combining modern learning activities (Manan & Hanafi, 2020).

Blended learning is the formal education program in which students learn the content and instruction of the subjects while also using online resources that allow them to have control over the time, place, pace, and progress of the courses. It is a hybrid learning activity that increases learning effectiveness, improves learning convenience, improves institutional reputation because of the use of technology platforms, reduces costs related to instructor reduction, lowers demand for university and school physical space, reduces motor vehicle traffic, and reduces parking congestion, among others.

Academic performance of students is the ability to study and remember facts and be able to communicate the knowledge orally or in written form as in a test, assignment, project, or examination condition (Yusuf, Afolabi, & Loto, 2015). However, different students have different factors responsible for their academic performance. This might include attitude towards school, interest in learning, study habits, attribution, self-efficacy, intelligence, and motivation. Students' academic performance cannot be completely accounted for by only one or two variables but by a number of them. Since students' academic performance depends on a number of variables, performance could be enhanced through identifying and manipulating each of such variables. A student's successful performance in any activity is based upon the volume of requisite information that he or she has on the activity, his or her interpretation of it, and most importantly, the application of his or her entire information on it. Acquisition of such information depends on reading and learning abilities that transmute between traditional and blended learning approaches.

As stated by Kiran (2017), blended learning incorporates both face-to-face and online teaching. Thus, integrate direct instruction, collaborative teaching, and individualized assisted learning. This process facilitates offline and online teaching and learning platforms (Alfi, Sumarmi, S., & Amirudin, 2016). In blended learning, the mixture of face-to-face and online teaching and learning is conveyed by using a variety of learning resources, media, and strategies to ease lecturers and student's communication processes.

Additionally, blended learning is not only used to introduce students to technology but also to support students who are less competitive or considered weaker in terms of cognitive ability. In other words, it encourages individuality, cultural diversity, power-sharing, and greater freedom in colleges, a perspective that, in compensation, requires a reinforced model and a critical curricular structure, protected by a change in learning that leads to more productive and interactive learning processes. Moreover, Blended Learning consists of a more flexible learning modality, and for this reason, it has been gaining more adherence among postgraduate students of educational management as an alternative to traditional learning models, thus expanding and liberating access to performance.

Blended Learning as a tech-instructive approach is used to describe the way that e-learning is combined with traditional classroom methods and creates a hybrid teaching methodology. The blended teaching methods offer more opportunities for lecturers and students to use different methods. Different learning styles can be accommodated by the use of blended learning, which results in self-learning, comprehension, and retention of information.

Statement of the Problem

Blended learning is an approach that integrates traditional face-to-face learning with a computer-mediated learning environment. Blended-learning environments produce improved student outcomes and results to facilitate the acquisition of competencies that may not otherwise be achieved. This approach can increase student engagement with the learning process, enhance critical-thinking development, and improve learning outcomes. A growing body of literature highlights the need to rethink the approach to classroom learning that adequately describes pedagogical innovations that foster higher-order thinking, improve information analysis and learning skills, and enhance opportunities for active and applied learning. These approaches represent an ongoing paradigmatic shift in education from teacher-centered instructional

strategies to blended learning that effectively integrates various learning activities and to active engagement of students.

Despite significant changes from the traditional approach to blended learning to the initial best ability of the students, there are still challenges associated with the improvement in student academic performance associated with blended learning. In other words, the blended learning models such as rotational, flex, self, and online driver models still pose problems based on a lack of computer skills from both the lecturers and students in initiating the current pedagogy. The question now is: how can the various blended learning models be applied to improve student's academic performance? Can the application of blended learning actually encourage students learning capacity? These are some of the questions that the researcher intends to answer, hence the research on influence of blended learning models on postgraduate students' academic performance of educational management at Rivers State Universities, Port Harcourt.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to examine influence of blended learning models on post graduate students' academic performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine how rotational model influence post graduate students' academic performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt.
2. Examine how flex model influence post graduate students' academic performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt.
3. Identify how self-blend model influence post graduate students' academic performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does rotational model influence post graduate students' academic performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt?
2. To what extent does flex model influence post graduate students' academic performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt?
3. To what extent does self-blend model influence post graduate students' academic performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in opinion of lecturers and post graduate students on how rotational model influence students' academic performance of educational management.
2. There is no significant difference in opinion of lecturers and post graduate students on how flex model influence students' academic performance of educational management.
3. There is no significant difference in the opinion of lecturers and post graduate students on how self-blend model influence educational management students' academic performance.

Significance of the study

The study will provide improved performance in terms of learning abilities of Educational Management students and other students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It will also promote flexibility of students through self-paced and time as well as increased application for blended learning facilities through share of knowledge across borders through online connectivity.

This study will serve as a reference point for academic purposes to future researchers including lecturers and students in the same problem area. Information from literature review, the research method and the result of this study will help them improve on their own research work.

The study will create awareness to educational management students on the blended learning model that will ensure the development of competencies and skills. In other words, the students will be motivated to attend conferences workshops, seminars as it relates to such internet skills in order to improve their academic researches.

The study will add to the volume of literature on Blended Learning Models and Post Graduate Students Academic Performance of Educational Management in the Universities, Port Harcourt.

Theoretical Framework

Connectivism Learning Theory

The connectivism learning theory is a theory that describes how people in the digital age learn through the transfer and sharing of information over the internet. The proponents of this theory are Siemens (2005) and Downes (2010), as cited in Bupo (2019), who tried to explain how the internet and all its applications have facilitated the way people share information and learn in an age that is technologically advancing by the day. The theory explains how digital technologies, especially those enabled by the internet like blogs, wikis, discussion forums, social media networks, emails, etc., can facilitate the learning process through information sharing.

The theory posits that learning starts when a learner connects to a learning community (online) and shares knowledge with members of the community. A learning community is blended together of like-minded people who have the same interests, and they encourage dialogue, information sharing, interaction, and discussions. Connectivism, according to Duke, Harper, and Johnston (2013), is "social learning that is networked". That is, learning that is facilitated by a network of people (called the learning group). This suggests that knowledge is shared across a network of connections, which therefore means that learning involves having the ability to connect with other people.

The implication of the connectivism learning theory for blended learning is that the teacher should be able to create a learning environment in which students can connect with each other through discussion forums, chats, emails, and peer review assignments. A blended learning approach that adopts connectivism theory will create the opportunity for students to learn by interacting with their peers online through peer review assignments and discussion forums.

Rotational model and students' academic performance

The Station Rotation Model (SRM) form of blending learning is advantageous as it rotates between different types of classrooms: online and offline, classes with the lecturers, and collaborative activities. Rotation could be from online to project, seminar, assessment, or paper assignments. It triumphs in education because it allows lecturers to monitor students' performance as a group or as individuals, allowing for effective student evaluation. The rotational model allows the application of technology in learning, especially in reading comprehension, the development of effective communication skills, and content delivery, allowing the students to experience the wholeness of classroom processes and experiences. In other words, the students become active, meaningful learners through cooperation and engaged learning with curiosity (Ogude & Chukweggu, 2019).

The rotation model, its effect on performance, and its influence have to do with the retrieval of information necessary for learning. It is not necessarily a process observable and carried out in schools but is a basic skill individuals engage in classroom situations (Kim, 2013). The rotational blended learning strategy incorporates different models that reflect a wide selection of educational technological innovations that transform the education process and improve students' acquisition of meaningful knowledge. The use of this model is critical because it determines the entire approach to instruction in terms of design and pedagogy.

Benefits of the Rotation Model

Personalized learning experiences among lecturers and students in this case, the lecturer or trainer is able to pay closer attention to and support individual learners. In other words, the lecturers and students should create dynamic lesson plans that better address individuals' or groups' specific learning needs. Variety in learning methods improves knowledge retention. By rotating through varied learning stations, learners benefit from repetition and increased engagement with the subject matter, which helps them retain memory.

It enhances collaborative learning, whether peer-to-peer or in larger groups. It involves students working in pairs or small groups to discuss concepts or find solutions to problems. Development of higher-level thinking, oral communication, self-management, and leadership skills; promotion of student-faculty

interaction; increase in student retention, self-esteem, and responsibility; and exposure to and an increase in understanding of diverse perspectives

Limitations of the rotation model

It's also worth considering the challenges of the station rotation model:

Lacks the agency of other blended learning models. The learners are moved through the process after a fixed time; for some, this time may not be enough for them to grasp the learning at their own pace. Other blended models, such as the flipped classroom, enable students to learn at their own pace, in their own time, outside of the classroom.

Requires investment in e-learning technology. This requires initiation from the organization or school, both in terms of devices and e-learning programs or tools. However, the benefits of incorporating e-learning into this model and organizing rotation lessons are fundamental and avoidable as students are guided through the learning processes.

The rotation model doesn't work for all subjects: Some practitioners have found this model doesn't work well in situations where learners must progress on a specific topic week by week, such as mathematics. This is because there could be some technical problems hindering internet access, a technological competency gap, lecturers' workload, a delay in feedback on students' assignments, or weak audio and video connectivity during lesson activities.

Flex model and students' academic performance.

The educational system has experienced a lot of transition based on the dynamics of society and nature. Teaching and learning in the study have migrated from traditional approaches to integrated approaches that require collaborative and flexible application of knowledge and skills for the expected performance of the students. Hence, flexible learning supports personalized learning, where learners' needs, interests, backgrounds, and learning styles are central. It reflects a shift from teacher-centered pedagogies and practices towards more innovative, student-centered approaches (Wanner & Palmer, 2015). Studies have indicated that flexibility is perceived as beneficial to online instruction.

A flexible model of blending learning permits flexibility regarding learning resources. This includes (a) the modality and origin of study materials; (b) the amount of content; (c) the sequence of different parts of a course and study routes; (d) assessment standards; and (e) completion requirements. Unlike traditional learning environments, which typically require students to follow a linear sequence, this model creates an environment that allows learners to follow a more individualized approach. This necessitates viewing the instructional material in a sequence that best meets their needs, repeating or skipping sections, and following subjects regardless of the order in which they have been arranged. Moreover, audio and video formats enable students to control the pace at which they consume and review content (Neville, Palmer, Elder, Fulford, Morris, & Sappington, 2015). Flexibility regarding content may range from being completely open, where the learner makes all the choices, to providing options within a particular framework established by the instructor.

Nevertheless, flexible learning environments require students to exercise control over different aspects of their learning activities, such as time management, type of media accessed, pace, and depth. In this situation, a learning environment is created where students need to be organized, set their own objectives and plans, and regulate and evaluate the learning process themselves (You, 2016). Flexible learning has shifted the entire focus of education from the instructor's teaching to the student's learning. Students were previously required to simply listen in class and then memorize information for a final exam. However, flexible learning is forcing institutions to rethink how students are taught and whether this traditional method of teaching is ultimately beneficial.

Every student has a different learning style, but traditional education does not cater to them all. Therefore, by changing the teaching styles and the way that students are presented with information, institutions are able to measure its overall impact and outcome. By providing students with the liberty to teach themselves and experiment with various learning methods, the student not only becomes more accountable for the way that they are digesting information, but it also helps to shift the responsibility

onto the student. When students feel more responsible for their learning, they are more likely to be dedicated and therefore work harder.

Institutions are quickly recognizing the value and impact of online learning components and are now beginning to implement them into their teaching. This not only helps to keep students engaged but also saves time because teachers do not have to allocate tasks in the classroom. Some courses expect students to participate in online quizzes and discussions aside from attending class, which can contribute to students being more interactive while being fully engaged in the things that they are learning.

The flexibility of online learning itself allows for more self-discipline and also helps students gain life skills that they can later implement in the workplace. This is something that is often neglected in traditional education, whereby students do not prioritize self-growth while having to constantly attend classes. Being able to demonstrate that they have acquired these skills through online learning can ultimately contribute to the student acquiring a more senior position within an organization. Therefore, flexibility itself has an enormous impact on the way that students learn, so its alluring nature has complete validity. Providing an individual with the option of how they learn is integral to their success.

Benefits of the flexible model of blended learning for students

- Allow students to learn where and when it suits them.
- Be economically viable for the students and make the best use of the available staff.
- Increase participation in learning
- Meet the access needs of a wide range of learners
- Make the best use of accommodation
- Develop more adaptable and responsive staff
- Build learners' confidence and independence
- Respond to the preferred learning styles of different learners
- Increase retention and attendance.
- Improve achievement and success rates, and
- Enable staff within your own organization to gain new knowledge and skills.

Self-blended model and students' academic performance.

Blended learning is an educational strategy that combines conventional education with online learning. For example, students could take an online course to learn the basics of a topic but then attend an in-person seminar to engage with experts and up their skills directly (Velangini, 2020).

One of the key benefits of the self-blend model is that it is so flexible. Thus, it can be used to support core education and allow students who have fallen behind in the basics to catch up; it is also advantageous for students seeking a further specialization.

The self-blend model of blended learning is a convenient means of offering education to students where it would otherwise be impractical. However, since nearly all of the education is delivered without a lecturer in this model, it can lead to simple misunderstandings that a lecturer would resolve if they were present to support the learning.

Like other forms of blended learning, the self-blend model makes use of online educational content, which can be delivered through a plethora of digital devices. The students themselves make progress with their course either via remote engagement with their tutor, who could be in another location entirely, or by organizing their own education from suitable resources they find online.

Self-blending is a program-level model that learners use to take online courses in addition to their traditional face-to-face courses. The self-blend model of blended learning relies almost exclusively on online learning. Although students may use computer labs within their school or college and receive assistance from teachers about how to access online resources, what they access and when they do so is usually entirely up to the student concerned. Indeed, the self-blend model does not rely on classroom-based activities at all. Students can just as easily complete a course that is delivered through the self-blend model at home or in a cyber-lounge as they might in a classroom that happens to have a networked computer (Neville, et al ,2015).

The self-blend model of blended learning is a convenient means of offering education to students where it would otherwise be impractical. However, since nearly all of the education is delivered without a teacher in this model, it can lead to simple misunderstandings that a teacher would resolve if they were present to support the learning. That said, the flexibility and degree of specialization that this model offers mean that it is likely to remain popular among students and educators alike.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive design to examine Influence of Blended Learning Models on post graduate students Academic Performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt. The population of the study was two hundred and twenty-five (225) lecturers and postgraduate students in the Department of Educational Management, Rivers State Universities. The sample of the study is 225 (lecturers and students) respondents. All the population was used as the sample size since it is small. The instrument was titled: Blended Learning Model and Post Graduate Students’ Academic Performance Questionnaire (BLMPGSAPQ). The questionnaire contains twenty (28) structured items using modified likert type scale of: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Very Low Extent (VHE) (VHE), Low Extent (LE).

The reliability was achieved using test-retest and Cronbach Alpha statistics which yielded the index of 0.74, 0.82, 0.77 and 0.87. Thus, 225 copies of questionnaire were administered and retrieved (195) for the analysis of research questions and hypotheses. The hypotheses were tested by the application z -test. The rule is to accept the hypothesis where the calculated z- value is less than critical z- value of +/- 1.96 at 0.05, but reject the hypothesis where the calculated z-value of +/- 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS:

Research Question 1: *To what extent does rotational model influence post graduate students’ academic performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt?*

Table 4.1: Mean response on the extent to which rotational model and students’ academic performance

S/N	Statement	Items	LECTURERS n=58		Decision	STUDENTS n=137		Decision
			Mean	Std.		Mean	Std.	
1	Incorporates different models with wide selection of learning activities that enhance students’ academic performance.		3.44	0.81	HE	3.66	0.67	HE
2	Improve students’ acquisition of meaningful Knowledge		3.56	0.67	HE	3.67	0.85	HE
3	Allows the application of technology in learning thus develop effective communication skills.		3.78	0.77	HE	3.66	0.74	HE
4	Transforms remote learning for enhancement of academic performance.		3.65	0.69	HE	2.67	0.76	HE
5	Creates more opportunities for collaboration		2.66	0.81	HE	3.55	0.77	LE
	Grand total		3.42	0.75	HE	3.44	0.79	HE

Table 4.1 above for research question one shows the mean responses of male and female respondents on the extent to which rotational model of learning influences academic performance among post graduate students of educational management. Item 1 has mean scores of 3.44 and 3.66, standard deviation of 0.81 and 0.67. Item 2 have mean scores of 3.56 and 3.67, standard deviation of 0.67 and 0.85. Item 3 have mean scores of 3.78 and 3.66, standard deviation of 0.77 and 0.74. Item 4 have mean scores of 3.65 and 2.67, standard deviation of 0.68 and 0.76. Item 5 have mean scores of 2.66 and 3.55, standard deviation of 0.81 and 0.77. The grand mean is 3.42 and 3.44, standard deviation of 0.75 and 0.79. This indicates that

both the male and female respondents agreed that to a high extent, that rotation model of learning influences academic performance of students of educational management in the Rivers State Universities.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does flex model influence post graduate students' academic performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt?*

Table 4.2: Mean responses on extent to which flex model and students' academic performance

S/N	Statement Items	LECTURERS n=58		Decision	STUDENTS n=137		Decision
		Mean	Std.		Mean	Std.	
6	Flexibility in learning cause innovation practice and build new experiences thus promote student academic performance	2.34	0.77	HE	3.22	0.72	HE
7	Design appropriate assessment though flexible learning activities influence students academic performance	3.14	0.71	HE	3.09	0.67	HE
8	Using flexible learning management system platform activate educational management students learning activities.	2.92	0.84	HE	2.71	0.81	HE
9	Flexible model increase in educational management student retention, self-esteem, and responsibility in the academic activities	3.11	0.87	HE	3.67	0.81	HE
10	Integrating flexible learning model make learning relevant to educational management students .	3.71	0.83	HE	3.11	0.96	HE
	Grand total	3.04	0.80	HE	3.16	0.79	HE

Table 4.1 above for research question one shows the mean responses of male and female respondents on the extent to which flex model of learning influences academic performance among post graduate students of educational management. Item 1 has mean scores of 2.34 and 3.22, standard deviation of 0.77 and 0.72. Item 2 have mean scores of 3.14 and 3.09, standard deviation of 0.71 and 0.67. Item 3 have mean scores of 2.92 and 2.71, standard deviation of 0.71 and 0.81. Item 4 have mean scores of 3.11 and 3.67, standard deviation of 0.87 and 0.81. Item 5 have mean scores of 3.71 and 3.11, standard deviation of 0.83 and 0.96. The grand mean is 3.04 and 3.16, standard deviation of 0.80 and 0.79. This indicates that both the male and female respondents agreed that to a high extent, that flex model of learning influences academic performance of students of educational management in the Rivers State Universities.

Research Question 3: *To what extent does self-blend model influence post graduate students' academic performance of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities, Port-Harcourt?*

Table 4.2: Mean responses on extent self-blend model and students' academic performance

S/N	Statement Items	LECTURERS n=58		Decision	STUDENTS n=137		Decision
		Mean	Std.		Mean	Std.	
11	Development of self-management skills that enhance student academic performance	3.11	0.81	Low Extent	3.76	0.77	High Extent
12	Linking students with other technological platform	3.76	0.88	High Extent	2.61	0.81	High Extent
13	Making available other resource materials that enhance learning performance.	2.43	0.70	High Extent	3.76	0.84	High Extent
14	Producing digitalize learning that enhances academic performance.	3.45	0.72	High Extent	2.78	0.87	High Extent
15	Aids in effective communication and interaction in knowledge and skills	3.47	0.88	High Extent	3.80	0.82	High Extent
	Grand total			High			High

Table 4.3 above for research question one shows the mean responses of male and female respondents on the extent to which self-blend model of learning influences academic performance among post graduate students of educational management. Item 1 has mean scores of 3.11 and 3.76, standard deviation of 0.81 and 0.77. Item 2 have mean scores of 3.76 and 2.61, standard deviation of 0.88 and 0.81. Item 3 have mean scores of 2.43 and 3.76, standard deviation of 0.70 and 0.84. Item 4 have mean scores of 3.45 and 2.78, standard deviation of 0.72 and 0.87. Item 5 have mean scores of 3.47 and 3.80, standard deviation of 0.88 and 0.82. The grand mean is 3.24 and 3.34, standard deviation of 0.79 and 0.82. This indicates that both the male and female respondents agreed that to a high extent, that self-blend model of learning influences academic performance of students of educational management in the Rivers State Universities.

Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in opinion of respondents on how rotational model influence Academic Performance of Post Graduate Students of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4.5: Using Z-Test Statistic on difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent to which rotational model influences academic performance .

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Z-cal	Z-crit	Level of Sign.	Decision
LECTURERS	58	3.42	0.75	193	1.54	1.96	0.05	Accepted
STUDENTS	137	3.44	0.79					

Table 4.5 above, shows that z – calculated value of 0.68 is less than (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance and 193 degree of freedom indicating that there is no significant difference between the responses of male and female respondents on the extent to which rotational model influences academic performance of students. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted

Ho₂: There is no significant different in opinion of respondents on how flex model influence Academic Performance of Post Graduate Students of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities educational management students’ academic performance.

Table 4.6: Using Z – Test Statistic on difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent to which flex model influences academic performance .

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Z- cal	Z-crit	Level of Sign.	Decision
LECTURERS	58	3.04	0.80	193	1.44	1.96	0.05	Accepted
STUDENTS	137	3.16	0.79					

Table 4.6 above, shows that z – calculated value of 0.44 is less than z-crit (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance and 193 degree of freedom indicating that there is no significant difference between male and female respondents on the extent to which flex model influences academic performance. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the opinion of respondents on how self-blend model influence Academic Performance of Post Graduate Students of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities.

Table 4.7: Using Z-Test Statistic on difference in the mean ratings of male and female respondents on the extent to which the adoption of self-blend model influences academic performance.

Respondents	N	\bar{X}	SD	Df	Z-cal	Z-crit	Level of Sign.	Decision
LECTURERS	58	3.24	0.79	193	0.49	1.96	0.05	Accepted
STUDENTS	137	3.34	0.82					

Table 4.7 above, shows that z – calculated value of 0.49 is less than z-crit (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance and 193 degree of freedom indicating that there is no significant difference between the responses of male and female respondents on the extent to which self-blend model influences academic performance. This therefore means that the null hypothesis is accepted.

Ho4: There is no significant difference in opinion of respondents on how online driver model influence Academic Performance of Post Graduate Students of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from the study of research question one revealed to a high extent of which rotation approach influence Academic Performance of Post Graduate Students of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities. Result of hypothesis 1 also shows that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of lecturers and post graduate students' response on the extent to which utilization of rotation model influences academic performance of post graduate students of Educational Management.

This finding is in agreement with the position of Kim (2013) who proposed that rotating model is fit enough and incorporates different models that reflect a wide selection of educational technological innovations that transform the education process and improve students' acquisition of meaningful knowledge. The use of this model is critical because it determines the entire approach to instruction in terms of design and pedagogy. In other words, it accommodates varied learning model, which students to retain memory thus aid in developing of higher-level thinking, oral communication, self-management, and leadership skills; promotion of student-faculty interaction; increase in student retention, self-esteem, and responsibility; and increase learning in a global, wide and diverse perspectives.

The finding is also in line with assertion of Ogude et al (2019), asserted that the learning environment may be entirely controlled by the students through use of rotational model, or it may be entirely controlled by the lecturer or instructor through the use of the lecture method, as a result of the use of multimedia. Thus the application rotational model to be useful and purposeful, the learning environment must be conducive and harmless or safe before, during, and after the learning process.

The findings in research question two indicated to a high extent of which flex model influence Academic Performance of Post Graduate Students of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities. Result of hypothesis two revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of lecturers and post graduate students' response on the extent to which utilization of flex model influences academic performance of post graduate students of Educational Management.

This finding is in-line with the discovery of Wanner et al (2015) who affirmed the educational system has experienced a lot of transition based on the dynamics of society and nature. In other words, teaching and learning in the study have migrated from traditional approaches to integrated approaches that require collaborative and flexible application of knowledge and skills for the expected performance of the students. Hence, flexible learning supports personalized learning, where learners' needs, interests, backgrounds, and learning styles are central. It reflects a shift from teacher-centered pedagogies and practices towards more innovative, student-centered approaches.

In support of the above, Neville, *et al.* (2015) asserted that a flexible model of blending learning permits flexibility regarding learning resources. This includes: the modality and origin of study materials, the amount of content, and the sequence of different parts of a course and study routes, assessment standards and completion requirements. This implies that Flexible learning has shifted the entire focus of education from the instructor's teaching to the student's learning. Students were previously required to simply listen in class and then memorize information for a final exam. However, flexible learning is forcing institutions to rethink how students are taught and whether this traditional method of teaching is ultimately beneficial. Every student has a different learning style, but traditional education does not cater to them all. Therefore, by changing the teaching styles and the way that students are presented with information, institutions are able to measure its overall impact and outcome. By providing students with the liberty to teach themselves and experiment with various learning methods, the student not only becomes more accountable for the way that they are digesting information, but it also helps to shift the responsibility onto the student. When students feel more responsible for their learning, they are more likely to be dedicated and therefore work harder.

Findings of the study indicated that flipped Classroom influence Academic Performance of Students in Selected Private Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis to a high extent. This is confirmed in the result of hypothesis 3 that there is no significant difference between male and female respondents on the extent to which the adoption of flipped classroom approach influences academic performance of students in selected private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Metropolis.

This finding is related to the observation of Gavrielides (2010), revealed that flip model is the usual classroom paradigm, in that students learn initial course concepts outside of the classroom, while class time is reserved for more active learning. The findings are also in line with the assertion of Agdur (2017), that flipped classroom dramatically increases the amount of time you have to spend with each student. It also create a platform for them to ask questions or seek extra help with an area they are finding challenging.

The findings in research question three indicated to a high extent of which self blended model influence Academic Performance of Post Graduate Students of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities. Result of hypothesis three revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of lecturers and post graduate students' response on the extent to which utilization of self blended model influences academic performance of post graduate students of Educational Management.

This findings is supported by the discovery in a study carried out by Neville, *etal* (2015), that Self-blending is a program-level model that learners use to take online courses in addition to their traditional face-to-face courses. The self-blend model of blended learning relies almost exclusively on online learning. Although students may use computer labs within their school or college and receive assistance from teachers about how to access online resources, what they access and when they do so is usually entirely up to the student concerned.

The study also revealed that self-blend model learning is a convenient means of offering education to students where it would otherwise be impractical. Like other forms of blended learning, the self-blend model makes use of online educational content, which can be delivered through a plethora of digital devices. The students themselves make progress with their course either via remote engagement with their tutor, who could be in another location entirely, or by organizing their own education from suitable resources they find online.

The findings in research question three indicated to a high extent of which online driver model influence Academic Performance of Post Graduate Students of Educational Management in Rivers State Universities.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that Blended learning method improves students' academic performance. In other words, it increased flexibility and independence of learning activities at

anytime and anywhere, letting students learn without the barriers of time and location but with the possible support of in-person engagement. Hence, increased interaction offers a platform to facilitate greater interactivity among the lecturers and students in the universities system.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. It was recommended that rotational model of teaching should be adopted to enhance the potentialities of post graduate students of educational management.
2. There should be application of team teaching to authenticate flexible learning activities within and outside the school environment.
3. There should be procedures and processes of generating assignments, on line test or tutorial to develop capacities for self-blended learning practice.

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